

SPATIAL DESIGN OF PIEZOELECTRIC SENSORS AND ACTUATORS FOR VIBRATION CONTROL OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

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SUMMARY: Distributed piezoelectric sensor and actuator have been designed for efficient vibration control of laminated composite plate. Electrode pattern of anisotropic piezoelectric film is adopted as design variables. Finite element method is used to model the structure that includes the piezoelectric sensor and actuator. To utilize the anisotropic characteristics of the PVDF film, various lamination angles of the PVDF transducer are considered.

Electrode of the PVDF film bonded over the plate is modeled with lots of small rectangular segments. Electrode pattern is optimized by deciding *on* or *off* of each electrode segment. Actuator design is based on the criterion of minimizing the system energy under a given initial condition. Sensor has been designed to minimize the observation spill-over. Modal forces for the residual modes have been selected as a performance index to be minimized during the sensor design. Genetic algorithm, which is suitable for this kind of discrete problems, is used for optimization. Discrete LQG is used to generate control law. Performance of the sensor, the actuator, and the integrated smart structure shows good agreement between analysis and experiment.

KEYWORDS: active vibration control, PVDF sensor and actuator design, distributed sensor/actuator, spatial filtering, electrode pattern

INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric materials are widely used as sensors and actuators in active vibration control of structures. Lead zirconate titanate (PZT) and polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) are most popular ones. As PVDF has different characteristics from PZT, there needs different approach to utilize its advantages. In this research, PVDF is used as a sensor and an actuator. Although PVDF has shortcomings such as small actuation force compared with PZT, the electrode of PVDF can be shaped easily. Easiness of electrode pattern shaping is a big merit of PVDF.

The active control of composite plates is usually more difficult than that of the isotropic one. This is mainly due to the possibility of high modal density of the composite structures. As modal density increases, control modes and residual (uncontrolled) modes can lie more closely in frequency domain. Then, the controller, a kind of time domain filter, cannot sufficiently fulfill the conflicting requirements: Large control gain in control modes; and the necessity to avoid the instability in residual modes caused by spill-over [1]. Spatial domain filtering by use of the distributed sensor/actuator is beneficial to this kind of difficulties.

As researches on the distributed sensor/actuator, Baliey and Hubbard [2] introduced the concept of spatial filter. Lee and Moon [3] proposed the modal sensor/actuator in beam

structure by changing the shape(width) of the electrode. As researches on the anisotropy of PVDF, Lee[4] devised a sensor and an actuator which can sense and actuate the torsional mode using the lamination angle. Yu, Kang and Kim[5] investigated the control effectiveness by changing the lamination angle of the PVDF actuator.

Modal sensor/actuator is a promising solution for the spill-over problem, but it can not be implemented in two-dimensional structures. In this research, modal sensor/actuator concept is extended to two-dimensional structure by introducing electrode segments and deciding the electrode pattern through optimization.

SYSTEM MODEL

Effect of Anisotropy of PVDF and the Electrode Shape

There exists reciprocity between piezoelectric sensor and actuator[6]. A piezoelectric sensor that yields large amount of charge for a specific vibration mode will have large actuating force for that mode when used as an actuator. Sensor equation derived by Lee[6] says that the amount of induced charge, q in a piezoelectric sensor is

$$\begin{aligned}
 q &= -z \int_S \left[\bar{e}_{31(xy)} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \bar{e}_{32(xy)} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} + \bar{e}_{36(xy)} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \right] dS \\
 &= \int_S \left[\bar{e}_{31(xy)} \varepsilon_x + \bar{e}_{32(xy)} \varepsilon_y + \bar{e}_{36(xy)} \frac{\gamma_{xy}}{2} \right] dS
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where, z is the distance from the neutral plane to the mid-plane of the sensor, and w is lateral displacement. S is the effective area of the sensor covered with electrode. \bar{e} 's and ε 's are piezoelectric constants and strain components, respectively. From the above equation, we can see that the amount of induced charge will increase if the piezoelectric sensor is located in highly strained region. Let's consider the case that the sign of strain changes from point to point in the region covered with a piezoelectric sensor. The charge induced in the positively strained area is canceled out by the charge induced in the negatively strained area, which leads to decrease of total induced charge. The piezoelectric constants, $\bar{e}_{ij(xy)}$, vary with the lamination angle of the anisotropic PVDF film. Therefore, both the electrode pattern and the lamination angle of the anisotropic PVDF transducer becomes more important. For PZT, the size and position of transducer have been given attentions in the same reason[7]. While PZT does not have any preferred direction in plane, PVDF has anisotropy. That is, its piezoelectric constant d_{31} is different from d_{32} , and consequently the piezoelectric constant e_{31} is different from e_{32} . Therefore, the sensing characteristics of the PVDF transducer vary with the lamination angle. The induced charge strongly depends on the lamination angle of the PVDF sensor. As the strain distribution is different from one vibration mode to another, the electrode shape that induces maximum charge will change from mode to mode.

Modeling of the Structure and Control Environment

Finite element method has been used to model the laminated composite plate integrated with piezoelectric sensor and actuator. The mass and stiffness of the integrated structure have been modeled using the Mindlin plate element with nine nodes. The piezoelectric sensor/actuator is divided into many rectangular electrode segments in each finite element. These electrode segments are determined to be *on* or *off* during the optimization process of the sensor/actuator.

Electrode of the segment selected to be *off* will be removed and thus this segment has no actuating force. All the segments selected to be *on* are electrically connected together. For example, let's assume 4 electrode segments in a plate element as shown in Fig. 1. If electrode segments ①, ②, and ③ are selected to be *on* and ④ is selected to be *off*, then the total actuation force by the piezoelectric actuator is as follows.

$$F_p = 1 \times (F_p^{(1)} + F_p^{(2)} + F_p^{(3)}) + 0 \times F_p^{(4)} \quad (2)$$

where, $F_p^{(i)}$ is the actuation force vector of i -th electrode segment. Notation of B_a instead of F_p will be used to represent the actuating force.

Equation of motion of the integrated structure is expressed as,

$$M\ddot{u} + Ku = B_a V_a \quad (3)$$

where, M and K are the mass matrix and stiffness matrices, respectively. u is discretized nodal displacement vector. Subscript a denotes actuator, and V_a is applied voltage.

Assuming modal viscous damping, Eqn 3 is expressed in modal coordinates. For computational efficiency, modal reduction is introduced;

$$\ddot{\eta}_R + c_R \dot{\eta}_R + \Lambda_R \eta_R = \Phi_R^T B_a V_a \quad (4)$$

where, η_R is a modal displacement, $c_R = \text{diag}(2\zeta_1\omega_1, \dots, 2\zeta_n\omega_n)$, $\Lambda_R = \text{diag}(\omega_1^2, \dots, \omega_n^2)$.

Φ_R is a matrix composed of eigenvectors. We define $\Phi_R^T B_a$ as modal force per unit voltage and it is used as a parameter for characterizing the piezoelectric sensors and actuators. If actuation force by a piezoelectric transducer is B_s , then charge induced to this transducer when used as a sensor is

$$q = B_s^T u. \quad (5)$$

A charge amplifier is used as an interfacing amplifier. The output signal through the amplifier is

$$y_{ca} = \frac{1}{C_a} B_s^T \Phi_R \eta_R. \quad (6)$$

where, $1/C_a$ is the gain of the charge amplifier.

Discrete LQG[8] has been used as a control law. To avoid aliasing, two low-pass filters have been used before the AD converter and after the DA converter. Filter was second order butterworth type. Since the size of the controller is limited by physical constraints, every structural mode can not be controlled. First two modes were selected to be controlled. These two modes have been considered during controller design. Fig. 2 shows the block diagram for the total system. The cut-off frequency of the low-pass filter was selected to lie between the third and fourth natural frequencies of the structure. These two filters in addition to the two structural modes will be considered during controller design. There are total eight state variables in the controller.

DESIGN OF SENSOR AND ACTUATOR

Electrode pattern of PVDF sensor/actuator with various lamination angles is optimized in this study. Genetic algorithm[9], which is suitable for this kind of discrete optimization problem, is used to decide whether a specific electrode segment is *on* or *off*. Schematic view of the integrated structure is shown in Fig. 4. The stacking sequence of the host structure is $[\pm 45^\circ]_s$. Mode shapes of the first two modes are presented in Fig. 5, and the natural frequencies of the first five modes are listed in Table 1. As shown in Fig. 5, the mode shape is unsymmetric

w.r.t. the center line, which comes from the coupling stiffness, D_{16} and D_{26} of the composite laminate. Therefore, PVDF transducer whose lamination angle of 45° and that of -45° have different modal effects. In this study, we adopted lamination angles of 45° , 30° , 15° , 0° , -15° , -30° , and -45° . With each lamination angle, optimal electrode pattern has been designed.

Among the natural frequencies of the integrated structure in this study, the second one and the third one are closely located. We decided to control the vibration upto the second mode. Time domain low-pass filter cannot successfully eliminate the signal that comes from the third mode vibration. And it is not desirable to use actuator that has the third and higher modal force components. PVDF sensor/actuator is optimized as follow:

Sensor Design Criteria

We want to maximize the modal forces for the control modes(1st and 2nd modes), and to minimize the modal forces for the residual modes(3rd to 5th mode). In other words, we want to maximize sensing signal from control modes, while minimizing that from the uncontrolled modes.

The performance index used is

$$J = \min(|\Phi_c^T B_s|) - \max(|\Phi_u^T B_s|) \quad (7)$$

where, subscript c and u represent the control and uncontrolled modes, respectively.

Actuator Design Criteria

System energy was selected as performance index:

$$J = E(0) / \int_0^\infty (\dot{\eta}_c^T \dot{\eta}_c + \eta_c^T \Lambda_c \eta_c + \rho g^T g) dt \quad (8)$$

Here $E(0)$ represents initial energy, and ρ is the weighting for the control signal g . This ρ does not affect the actuator design result. Specific mode can be weighted by changing the initial condition of the system. That is, if initial condition is pure first mode, then the acquired result will be a shape that maximizes the modal control force for the first mode. The larger a actuator retains modal actuation force in control mode, the sooner the system energy decays out. The system energy in the denominator in Eqn 8, therefore, will decrease.

Design Result and Discussion

To see the effect of anisotropy of the PVDF transducer, optimization of electrode pattern has been performed for various lamination angles. Selected initial conditions for the actuator design were pure first mode and pure second mode. Fig. 6 shows the variation of PVDF actuator's modal control forces with lamination angles. For comparison, modal control forces of actuator whose electrode covers the entire surface of plate(labeled AC) are included together. Optimized results in Fig. 6(a) are obtained with the initial condition of pure first mode and Fig. 6(b) with the initial condition of pure second mode.

From Fig. 6(a), we can see that there are not much differences in modal force between the optimized ones and those labeled AC. As the strain distribution of the first mode shape is of the same sign over the entire surface, almost all electrode segments are *on* except a few segments. Modal control forces for positive lamination angles differ from that for negative lamination angles. Unsymmetry of mode shape about the center line causes this difference.

Design results for the second mode show more severe unsymmetry. Differences exist between the optimized ones and those labeled *AC*. This is due to the fact that the second mode has relatively more complex (sign changing) strain distribution. The lamination angle which shows maximum control for the second mode is -45° as shown in Fig. 6(b). This also can be explained from the mode shape. As shown in Fig. 5, the second mode deflects more flexibly along the -45° direction and therefore has larger normal strain in that direction. Consequently, -45° lamination angle shows maximum force.

Based on the design criteria for PVDF transducer explained above, an actuator [labeled *A2(-30°)*] and a sensor [labeled *S(-15°)*] have been chosen for our integrated smart structure. Electrode patterns of these transducers are shown in Fig. 7. All the electrode segments in black are electrically connected together. Modal control forces of these transducers are listed in Table 2. Label, *A2(-30°)* means optimized actuator design result for the 2nd mode with lamination angle of -30° . Label, *S(-15°)* indicate optimized sensor with lamination angle of -15° . To show the effect of electrode pattern optimization, additional two transducers are included in Table 2. Labels, *AC(-15°)* and *AC(-30°)* mean that the electrode covers the entire surface of plate with lamination angles of -15° and -30° , respectively.

From Table 2, we can clearly see that the sensor, *S(-15°)* retains very small modal forces for the residual modes. Modal forces for the control modes are large enough. Therefore, the output signal from the residual modes can be negligible. This sensor is a kind of band-stop filter in modal coordinates.

Concerning the characteristics of actuator, the 2nd modal force of *A2(-30°)* is larger than that of *AC(-30°)* and *AC(-15°)*. This is the result of electrode pattern optimization.

EXPERIMENT

Experiment has been carried out to show the performance of our integrated structure. Transfer functions of the designed PVDF sensor and actuator are obtained by the impact hammer test. Experimental result has been compared with the result from analysis. During digital control using LQG, we get the closed-loop transfer function. Comparing this with the transfer function of sensor, we have demonstrated the vibration control capability of our integrated structure.

Specimen Preparation

Composite laminate was fabricated with HFG HT145/RS1222 carbon/epoxy prepreg. Nominal thickness of the prepreg is 0.125mm. Standard curing cycle recommended by the prepreg manufacturer is followed. Thickness of the PVDF film used in this experiment is 52 μ m. Photosensitizer is applied over the entire surface of PVDF film and dried in temperature controlled oven. After being exposed to light through the negative image of the optimized electrode pattern, the film is developed to leave protective coating on the active electrodes. Evaporatively deposited copper-nickel electrode is chemically etched out to shape the optimized electrode pattern. Ferric chloride is used as etchant. After washing out the etchant with water and the PVDF film is dried in air. The PVDF sensor is bonded on one surface and the actuator on the other surface with epoxy adhesive. Integrated structure is completed by attaching the electric lead wire and mounts for fixture.

Experimental Setup

Fig. 3 shows the experimental setup. The charge amplifier gain is 10^8 Volt/Farad and cut-off frequency of the low-pass filter is 100 Hz. Sensing signal is digitally sampled 5000 times per second at the AD converter just before the controller. Control output through the DA converter is limited to ± 4 Volt and applied to actuator via the high voltage amplifier whose gain is set to 100 Volt/Volt.

Excitation force from the impact hammer and the sensing signal from the charge amplifier are processed at the FFT analyzer to yield the transfer function of the integrated structure.

Experimental Result and Discussion

Experimentally obtained transfer functions are shown in Figs. 8(a) ~8(c). Comparing with the modal control forces listed in Table 2, designed PVDF sensor and actuator behave as expected in the finite element analysis. We can discriminate against the signal which comes from the residual modes with our optimized sensor, $S(-15^\circ)$. This is helpful to reduce the effect of observation spill-over. Our optimized actuator, $A2(-30^\circ)$, can effectively excite the structure to the second mode. Although the actuator retains modal forces of higher modes, the associated sensor does work to retard the instability of the integrated structure. Transfer function of the closed-loop system in Fig. 8(c) and that of the open-loop system in Fig. 8(a) show the vibration reduction in the amount of 9dB and 11dB for the first and the second modes, respectively.

CONCLUSION

Design methodology for distributed PVDF sensor and actuator for vibration control of laminated composite plate has been presented. Using the anisotropy of the PVDF film and the electrode shaping, PVDF transducer, which works as a spatial filter, has been designed. It is an extension of the concept of modal transducer to two-dimensional structure. Lamination angle of the PVDF film has influence on the characteristics of the transducer.

Sensor has been optimized to reduce the observation spill-over, and actuator has been optimized to maximize the modal force for a specific vibration mode. We can successfully reduce the signal from the residual modes and increase the modal force of the control mode. Experimental verification has been accomplished for the performance of the optimized sensor and actuator. Real time vibration control has been accomplished for the laminated composite plate integrated with the optimized sensor and actuator.

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Table 1: Natural frequencies of the integrated structure, in Hz

1st mode	2nd mode	3rd mode	4th mode	5th mode
14.0	66.4	86.1	199.6	233.6

Table 2: Modal control force of various electrode shapes

	AC(-15°)	ACI(-30°)	A2(-30°)	S(-15°)
1st mode	-3.7871e-4	-3.3355e-4	-2.7252e-4	-3.0736e-4
2nd mode	9.7002e-4	1.2114e-3	1.3716e-3	5.4544e-4
3rd mode	-7.0975e-4	-3.5084e-4	-5.7741e-4	-4.9298e-6
4th mode	-1.7810e-3	-2.1646e-3	-1.9190e-3	2.8636e-6
5th mode	-8.0549e-4	-2.9311e-4	2.1256e-4	1.7926e-6

Fig. 1: A finite element with 4 electrode segments

Fig. 2: Block diagram for the total system

Fig. 3: Experimental Setup

Fig. 4: Schematic view of the specimen

Fig. 5: Mode shapes of the integrated structure

(a) Variation of Modal Control Forces for the First Mode

(b) Variation of Modal Control Forces for the Second Mode

Fig. 6: Variation of modal control force by lamination angle and electrode shape

(a) A2 (-30°)

(b) S (-15°)

Fig. 7: Electrode patterns of the optimized transducers (L.H.S. edges are fixed boundary)

Fig. 8(a): Open-loop Transfer Function of Optimized Sensor, $S(-15^\circ)$

Fig. 8(b): Open-loop Transfer Function of Optimized Actuator, $A2(-30^\circ)$

Fig. 8(c): Closed-loop Transfer Function of Integrated Structure